

Resin-membrane Electrodes without Using any Binder

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Two homogeneous cation-selective resin membranes by the reaction of pyrocatechol with formaldehyde and of *p*-phenolsulphonic acid with formaldehyde have been prepared without the use of any binder, but allowing the substances to polymerise in the form of membranes. The electrochemical behaviour of these two types of membranes has been studied by measuring K^+ and Na^+ ion activities in electrolytic solutions. The range of validity is found to be $\alpha=0.00098$ to $\alpha=0.070$ for both K^+ and Na^+ . From general considerations, these membranes seem to show no particular advantage over those with the binder except that the method of preparation is less troublesome.

Membranes, prepared from ion-exchange materials, have widely been used as electrodes for the measurement of ionic activities, namely, clay¹ membranes of Marshall¹, collodion membranes of Sollner², ion-exchange resin membranes of Wyllie and Patnode³. Since the introduction of resin-membrane electrodes, Sinha⁴ used them in a slightly modified way to measure the cation and anion activities, namely, of Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} ions in electrolytic solutions. The work was extended by Basu⁵ for studying the activities of heavy metal ions like Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , and Mn^{2+} . Basu⁶ has also measured the activities of anions like Br^- , I^- , BrO_3^- , IO_3^- , and NO_3^- .

While preparing the resin-membrane electrodes, emphasis was laid to the pressure employed in moulding them. The pressure ought to be high enough to make the ion-exchange resin as uniformly distributed as possible in the binder matrix. The performance of the resin is less satisfactory if this pressure is lower than ~ 4000 lbs. p. s. i. Apparently, the uniformity of composition of the membrane, both inside and on the surface, is an important factor. It is therefore of interest to study if a suitable membrane could be prepared without the use of the binder resin, but allowing the resin to polymerise in the form of a membrane.

Juda and McRae⁷ have announced the preparation of membranes from a sulphonic acid type cation-exchange resin, but the actual procedure has not been revealed. These membranes are commercially available in the form of supported sheets of thickness of several tenths of a millimeter.

1. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1939, **43**, 1155; 1941, **45**, 1911; 1944, **48**, 67.
2. *Ibid.*, 1945, **49**, 47, 171, 265; 1946, **50**, 470; 1947, **51**, 299.
3. *J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1950, **54**, 204.
4. *This Journal*, 1953, **30**, 520; 1954, **31**, 572, 577.
5. *Ibid.*, 1958, **35**, 451.
6. *This issue*, p. 619.
7. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 1044.

Kressman⁸ has briefly described membranes prepared as coherent sheets from a strong acid type ion-exchange resin as well as membranes consisting of a supporting material such as paper or cloth, which is impregnated with the resin.

Bonhoeffer *et al.*⁹ have described the electromotive properties of chips of strong and weak acid type cation-exchanger resin which were used as membranes.

Manecke¹⁰ has made a similar study with a cation-exchanger resin membrane, but the method of preparation is not known.

We have prepared two homogeneous cation-selective resin membranes by the reaction of pyrocatechol with formaldehyde and of *p*-phenolsulphonic acid with formaldehyde and studied their electrochemical behaviour. From the practical stand point no advantage has been recorded except that the method of preparation is simple. Physically, these membranes appear quite different from those described earlier. Their electrochemical properties are likely to be of theoretical importance.

EXPERIMENTAL

Pyrocatechol-formaldehyde Resin Membrane.—To pyrocatechol (≈ 1g.), dissolved in minimum amount of water in a small petri dish (about 4 cm. diam.), a saturated $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ solution (≈ 5ml) was added* followed by formaldehyde (8 ml, 40% by volume). The mixture was diluted with water to the capacity of the petri dish. It was then subjected to slow evaporation on a water bath, controlling its rate of evaporation such that it took about 3 hrs. for complete evaporation. During evaporation slow resinification occurred and when the evaporation was complete, an amber-coloured membrane was formed, which to all appearances looked homogeneous.**

p-Phenolsulphonic Acid-formaldehyde Resin Membrane.—To *p*-phenolsulphonic acid (≈ 6 ml), taken in a petri dish of about 8 cm. diam., was added formaldehyde (≈ 6ml, 40% by vol.). A small amount of water was added and the mixture thoroughly mixed. No catalyst was required. The amount of formaldehyde is often critical, but an excess of formaldehyde must be avoided otherwise the membrane becomes brittle. The mixture was then subjected to rapid evaporation on a water bath. Resinification began within a very short time. The solution became turbid with a slight pinkish colour. As drying proceeded, the membrane set and finally on prolonged heating on the water bath the colour changed to blackish grey. It was then detached from the dish by the same method as in the case of the catechol-formaldehyde membrane. The membrane

8. *Nature*, 1950, 165, 568.

9. *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1951, 198, 270, 281.

10. *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1951, 55, 672.

*Amongst the many catalysts tried, both acidic and alkaline, $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ was found to be the best.

**In order to loosen the strongly adhering membrane from the dish, hot water was poured into it while on the water bath, and heated further for about an hour. Gradually the membrane detached itself from the dish. It was then thoroughly washed with warm water and then kept immersed in a strong HCl solution for about 24 hrs.

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The thickness of the membranes formed was about 0.5 mm. The swelling was almost negligible both in acid solution and in pure water. These membranes could be kept exposed to the air for a long period without cracking. Thus prepared, these had to be cut with a sharp razor blade and rounded off with a file to the circular shape and then fixed as usual to one end of a pyrex tubing with "Durofix".

The membrane electrodes, so prepared, were then soaked in a strong neutral potassium chloride solution on both sides. But the interesting point was that even after two months of soaking, the membranes developed little or no electrochemical property. The E. M. F. readings were often erratic. After about a year of soaking in KCl solution, during which the membranes were occasionally tested, these were found to develop the desired electrochemical property. Moreover, appreciable swelling was observed, especially in the pyrocatechol-formaldehyde membrane. It was, however, noticed that once the membranes responded to potassium ion, they could be easily changed to sodium-ion form by keeping them in a strong neutral sodium chloride solution for two to three days only. The only difficulty appears to be the initial change from hydrogen to any other cation form. The dense packing of the membrane may be a possible reason. Once the packing is slightly loosened, the exchange of the interior hydrogen ions becomes easy. In KCl or NaCl solutions, made slightly alkaline, the swelling is so rapid that the membrane is often completely dispersed. If the membranes are changed from potassium or sodium form to the hydrogen form, these show cracks, perhaps owing to contraction. When once these initial difficulties are over, the membranes perform fairly satisfactorily, as the results recorded in Table I show. Equilibrium is also attained very quickly with concentrated solutions, but in very dilute solution a few hours are sometimes required.

TABLE I

Activities (Inside/outside).	Mean obs. E. M. F.		Theoretical E.M.F.	Mean obs. E. M. F.		Theoretical E.M.F.
	A. Potassium-ion activity.			B. Sodium-ion activity.		
	CF*.	PF*.	CF*.	PF**.		
0.00294/0.00098	27.8 mV	28.0 mV	28.1 mV	27.5 mV	27.8 mV	28.1 mV
0.00882/0.00294	27.5	27.8	28.1	27.8	27.8	28.1
0.02646/0.00882	27.5	27.5	28.1	27.6	27.6	28.1
0.07938/0.02646	26.2	27.0	28.1	26.0	27.0	28.1
0.23810/0.07938	22.5	23.0	28.1	23.0	22.0	28.1

*CF stands for pyrocatechol-formaldehyde resin membrane.

**PF stands for *p*-phenolsulphonic acid-formaldehyde resin membrane.

DISCUSSION

The agreement between the theoretical and the experimental values is fairly good within the range, $\alpha=0.00098$ to $\alpha=0.079$ for both K^+ and Na^+ ions. Of the two membranes, the phenolsulphonic acid-formaldehyde membrane seems to perform better than the

other, perhaps because of the stronger acidic property of phenolsulphonic acid compared to catechol, and hence of a higher charge density of its membrane surface.

FIG. 1. E.M.F. vs. $\log 1/a$ curve for Na^+ ion with $\alpha_1 : \alpha_2 = 3$.

FIG. 2. E.M.F. vs. $\log 1/a$ curve for K^+ ion with $\alpha_1 : \alpha_2 = 3$.

As in the case of binder membranes, the thickness is an important factor. Very thin membranes allow considerable osmosis, whereas very thick ones possess high electrical resistance. The optimum thickness can be easily attained by a suitable adjustment of the amount of membrane materials and also the area of the evaporating dish.

From general considerations, these membranes without binder seem to show no particular advantage over those with the binder except that the method of preparation is less troublesome. The initial difficulty in making the membrane work may perhaps be overcome. Preliminary experiments show that unless the membranes are thoroughly exchanged with bivalent ions, these are very poorly responsive to them. This and the other consideration, that the porosity of the membranes and possibly their charge may be suitably controlled, suggest that these may be developed so as to impart certain degree of specificity.

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